

POLICY EVOLUTION IN DRUG PREVENTION EFFORTS IN INDONESIA

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Abstract

Narcotics Abuse Survey in Indonesia conducted by BNN and LIPI in 2019, the prevalence rate of drug abuse in Indonesia reached 2.4% or equivalent to 4.5 million people. This view turned out to catch the government and the entire Indonesian nation off guard against the threat of the dangers of drugs. The focus of this study uses qualitative approach with a descriptive method. The author chose this method because the experience and understanding of facts and phenomena in the field so that this research prioritizes process over results. Findings, an effort to curb the abuse and illicit circulation of drugs, an evolution of policies is needed to provide a burden that can be felt directly by the community. The suggestion is that every change of leadership does not have to change the direction of policy in a revolutionary manner but can continue policies that are still relevant to be implemented.

Keywords: Policy Evolution, Drug Prevention.

A. BACKGROUND

Based on the results of the Narcotics Abuse Survey in Indonesia conducted by BNN and LIPI in 2019, the prevalence rate of drug abuse in Indonesia reached 2.4% or equivalent to 4.5 million people. With a mortality rate of 30-50 people dying daily, only about 13,320 addicts accessed rehabilitation services in 2019. While the rest are still scattered to all levels of society, both the family environment, work, education and community environment, in conditions of having narcotics addiction and potentially disturbing order and triggering problems in their environment.

The abuse and illicit circulation of drugs have been shown to damage the nation's future and human character, both physical and public health. In the long run, this problem will potentially interfere with the competitiveness and progress of the Indonesian nation. The impact of the

damage caused has become enormous, especially since the 1990s. Psychotropic drugs such as meth and ecstasy have flooded the black market in several areas in Indonesia.

Overcoming the dangers of narcotics abuse and illicit circulation in Indonesia began in 1971. The issuance of Presidential Instruction of the Republic of Indonesia (Inpres) Number 6 of 1971 to the Head of the National Intelligence Coordinating Board to overcome 6 main national problems. Namely, the eradication of counterfeit money, countering drug abuse, countering smuggling, overcoming juvenile delinquency, overcoming subversion, and supervision of foreigners. Based on the Presidential Instruction, the Head of BAKIN formed the Bakolak Inpres in 1971, one of whose duties and functions is to overcome the dangers of drugs. Bakolak Inpres is a small coordinating body comprising representatives from the Ministry of Health, Ministry of Social Affairs, Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Attorney General's Office, and others, which is under the command and responsible to the Head of BAKIN. This agency does not have operational authority and does not receive its budget allocation from ABPN, but it is provided based on BAKIN's internal policies.

At that time, the drug problem in Indonesia was still a small problem, and the New Order Government continued to view and believe that the drug problem in Indonesia would not develop because the Indonesian nation was a nation that had Pancasila and religion. This view turned out to catch the government and the entire Indonesian nation off guard against the threat of the dangers of drugs. So that when the drug problem exploded, accompanied by the regional currency crisis in mid-1997, the Indonesian government and nation seemed unprepared to face it, in contrast to Singapore, Malaysia and Thailand, which since 1970 have consistently and continuously fought the dangers of drugs. Facing the drug problem that continues to increase, the Government and the House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia (DPR-RI) passed Law Number 5 of 1997 concerning Psychotropics and Law Number 22 of 1997 concerning Narcotics. Based on these two laws, the Government (President Abdurahman Wahid) established the National Narcotics Coordinating Board (BKNN) with Presidential Decree Number 116 of 1999. BKNN is a Coordinating Board for Drug Control consisting of 25 relevant Government Agencies.

BKNN is chaired by the Chief of Police of the Republic of Indonesia (Kapolri) on an ex-officio basis. Until 2002 BKNN did not have its personnel and budget allocations. The BKNN budget was obtained and allocated from the Headquarters of the National Police of the Republic of Indonesia (Mabes Polri), so it could not carry out its duties and functions optimally. BKNN, as a coordinating body, felt inadequate to deal with the increasingly severe threat of drug dangers. Therefore, based on Presidential Decree Number 17 of 2002 concerning the National Narcotics Agency, BKNN was replaced with the National Narcotics Agency (BNN). BNN, as a forum institution tasked with coordinating 25 related government agencies and operational authorities, has the following duties and functions 1) coordinates relevant government agencies in the formulation and implementation of national policies on drug control and 2) coordinates the implementation of national drug countermeasures policies. Starting in 2003, BNN only received a budget allocation from the state budget. With the state budget allocation, BNN continues to strive to improve its performance together with BNP and BNK. However, because

the institutional structure does not have a firm command line and is only coordinative (functional similarity), the BNN is considered unable to work optimally and deal with severe and increasing drug problems. Therefore, the authority holder in this case immediately issued Presidential Regulation 83 of 2007 concerning the National Narcotics Agency, the Provincial Narcotics Agency (BNP) and the Regency/City. Narcotics Agency (BNK), which has operational authority through the authority of the relevant BNN Members in the task force, where BNN-BNP-BN district/cit is a partner at the national, provincial and district/city levels, each of which is responsible to the President, The Governor and Regent/Mayor, and each (BNP and BN Kab/Kota) have no structural-vertical relationship with BNN.

Responding to the development of the drug problem that continues to increase and is getting more serious, the MPR-RI Decree Number VI / MPR / 2002 through the General Assembly of the People's Consultative Assembly of the Republic of Indonesia (MPR-RI) in 2002 recommended the DPR-RI and the President of the Republic of Indonesia to make changes to Law Number 22 of 1997 concerning Narcotics. Therefore, the Government and the House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia passed and promulgated Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics as an amendment to Law Number 22 of 1997. Based on Law Number 35 of 2009, BNN is authorized to investigate narcotics crimes and narcotic precursors. Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics is the latest and last Law in the war on drugs. In this Law, it is also regulated that the BNN is given the authority to investigate and investigate criminal acts of narcotics and narcotic precursors. What BNN is fighting, for now, is a way to IMPOVERISH drug dealers or dealers because it is alleged and proven in some cases that drug sales have been used for terrorist financing (Narco-Terrorism) and also to avoid drug sales activities for political expenses (Narco for Politics)).

B. METHOD

The focus of this study uses qualitative methods with a descriptive approach to analysis. As proposed by Norman K. Denzin & Yvonna S Lincoln, (2011), qualitative methods state: "That qualitative research is a study that uses a natural setting, with the intention of interpreting phenomena that occur and are carried out by means of involving various existing methods. Meanwhile, the approach used in this study is descriptive-analytical. This research method solves problems based on the facts and realities and focuses on the issues that occurred when the research was carried out. The purpose of this descriptive study is to make an accurate description of the facts, properties and relationships between phenomena that occur.

This study aims to make a systematic, factual and accurate picture of the facts and relationships between the phenomena to be studied. The author chose this method because this method is considered following the problems and objectives of this study to get an idea of the experience and understanding of facts and phenomena in the field so that this research prioritizes process over results.

C. DISCUSSION

The problem of drug abuse and illicit circulation is complex, requiring all parties' involvement in dealing with it. The National Narcotics Agency is an institution that plays a significant role in overcoming the problem of drug abuse and illicit circulation in Indonesia, so the BNN has the primary task and function of moving all components of the nation in contributing to efforts to Prevent and Eradicate Narcotics Abuse and Illicit Circulation (P4GN) so that BNN has several policy strategies in dealing with these problems which over time continue to develop by the policies targeted by the government.

1. Policy Evolution in P4GN

Badan Narkotika Nasional as an institution that carries out a mandate in tackling the narcotics problem in Indonesia, is part of the seventh development agenda, namely strengthening the stability of the fields of Politics, Law, Defense, and Security and the transformation of public services, with the implementation of national priority programs, national priority activities and national priority projects. BNN's national priority projects consist of 1) Prevention and eradication of illicit circulation of narcotics and narcotic precursors and 2) Improvement of narcotics abuse prevention and rehabilitation of narcotics abuse.

Table 1: Policy Evolution in Drug Prevention

No	Year	Leader	Policy Direction
1	< 2009		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2003 Just got the state budget. 2009 The Narcotics Law was passed as a substitute for Law No. 22 of 1997.
2	2009-2014	Gories Mere	Strengthening regulation through: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Enactment of Law No. 35 of 2009. Sema No. 4 of 2010. Joint regulation of 7 agencies related to the handling of drug addicts.
		Anang Iskandar	Rehabilitation of 100,000 Pecancus.
3	2015-2020	Budi Waseso	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Balancing Supply Reduction with Demand Reduction. Reduce the prevalence rate of drug abuse by 0.1%
		Heru Winarko	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Internalization of organizational culture Indonesia Clean Drugs Program (Shining)
4	2021-2025	Petrus Reinhard Golose	Approach strategy through Hard Power Approach, Soft Power Approach and Smart Power Approach

Policy directions and strategies are prepared as an approach to solving problems in the 2020-2024 period and have an impact on achieving national goals. The policy direction of BNN in

2020-2024 contains stages to solve problems that are already complex and must be resolved and have a significant impact on the achievement of the vision, mission, goals and strategic objectives of BNN. Before entering the policy direction and strategy of the 2020-2024 BNN that will be determined, formulating the policy direction is first described. The method of preparing policy directions refers to the Regulation of the Minister of Vat Number 5 of 2019, which defines that the policy direction is the elaboration of government affairs and development priorities under the vision and mission of the President. Various policies are carried out to prevent drug abuse and illicit circulation in Indonesia. Based on the observations made by the researchers, every change of leadership in the policy direction tends to change. This happens because of the development of conditions of drug abuse and circulation that are constantly dynamic. The results of observations on the principle of leadership policies are outlined by researchers as follows:

Based on the table, it can be concluded that the leadership has a tendency to develop new patterns to prevent drug abuse and illicit circulation. Relating to these conditions, In general, Rossi et al., (2004) state four reasons why policy evaluations are carried out, namely to:

1. Assess the ongoing program's feasibility and estimate the improvement efforts' practicality.
2. Assess the practicality of innovative program initiatives.
3. Improve the effectiveness of program administration and management.
4. Meet various accountability requirements.

It becomes natural for the BNN to make a breakthrough through the evolution of policies to prevent drug abuse and illicit circulation. However, the policy tends to change every time there is a leadership change.

The evolution of policies carried out by BNN has been adjusted to the developments in Indonesia. The world, especially related to the prevention of drug abuse and illicit circulation, considers that the results of a policy implementation also, according to Grindle, are determined mainly by the level of implementability of the policy itself, which consists of the Content of Policy and Context of Policy. (Agustino Leo, 2014). The content of the policy, according to Grindle is:

- a) Interest Affected. Interest affected relates to the various attractions that influence policy implementation. This indicator is who is involved and how those interests influence their implementation. This is what you want to know more about.
- b) Type of benefits. Content of policy seeks to explain that in a policy, there must be several types of benefits and positive impacts produced by the implementation of the policy to be implemented.
- c) The extent of Change Envision (degree of change to be achieved). Each policy has a target to be completed. Content of policy is how much difference is to be achieved through a policy implementation must have a clear scale.

- d) Site of Decision Making. Decision-making in a policy plays an essential role in implementing a policy. Site of Decision Making. Decision-making in a policy plays a crucial role in implementing a policy. This section should explain where the decision-making of an approach to be implemented lies.
- e) Program Implementer (program implementer). In carrying out a policy or program, it must be supported by competent policy implementers for the success of the policy.
- f) Resources Committed (the resources used). The implementation of a policy must also be supported by supporting resources so that its implementation runs well.

Meanwhile, in the point of view of George C. Edwards III, there are four variables in public policy, namely 1) Communications 2) Resources 3) attitudes and 4) bureaucratic structure. The four factors must be implemented simultaneously and have a close relationship. Implementation of public policy according to George Edward III above, there are 4 (four) main elements that must be met so that policy implementation can run effectively. These elements are Communion (regarding how policies are communicated to organizations and or the public), Resources (regarding the availability of supporting resources, especially human resources), Disposition (regarding the willingness of implementors to implement such public policies) and. Bureaucratic structure (regarding the suitability of the bureaucratic organization implementing public policy).

2. Current P4GN Policy

The P4GNPN program is an implementation of overcoming drug problems against the development of drug abuse and illicit circulation in Indonesia. BNN continues to increase the intensity and extension of efforts to save the nation from abuse and illegal drug circulation by implementing P4GNPN. Determining a public issue to be raised on a government plan is very important. Policy issues are often referred to as policy problems. Policy issues occur because of cross-opinions between actors regarding the direction of action that has been or will be pursued or conflicting views on the character of the problem. According to William, (1994), policy issues are the product or function of a debate about the formulation, details, explanation and assessment of a particular problem. But in reality, not all issues can be included in the policy agenda. Regarding the policy in P4GNPN in Indonesia, it is currently carried out by prioritizing the principle of balance between demand reduction and supply reduction, as well as "common and share responsibility." Some of the P4GNPN programs are as follows:

Demand Reduction Side

To increase public knowledge, understanding, and awareness, especially among students, students, workers, families, and vulnerable/high-risk communities, of the dangers of drug abuse and illicit circulation, P4GNPN Communication, Information, and Education (IEC) has been carried out massively throughout Indonesia through the use of print media, electronic media, online media, traditional arts, face-to-face (counseling, seminars, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), workshops, workshops, etc.), as well as outdoor media. This is a form of fulfilling the community's wishes through easy access to information about drug abuse's

dangers. In addition, volunteers or cadres or anti-drug activists have also been formed, and community empowerment has been carried out in the educational environment, work environment, and community environment throughout Indonesia to build awareness, concern and independence of the community in protecting themselves, their families, and the domain from the dangers of drug abuse.

Supply Reduction Side

The eradication of illicit drug trafficking aims to break the availability of illegal drugs to reduce the growth rate of the prevalence rate. Public expectations for BNN's performance in this aspect of eradication are enormous. This can be seen in the high public interest in the coverage of national mass media reports every time there is a disclosure of a drug case. Over the past four years, there has been an increase in the revelations of cases and suspects of illicit drug trafficking crimes and disclosure of money laundering crimes (TPPU) stemming from drug crimes. Implementation of the P4GNPN Program by the Four Pillars of BNN. The pillars are: The Pillar of Prevention, the Pillar of Community Empowerment, the Pillar of Rehabilitation, and the last one is the Pillar of Eradication. The pillars each have implementation goals, program objectives, and activity goals, namely:

- a) Prevention Pillar Implementation Target is to increase the community's deterrent to the dangers of drug abuse and illicit circulation. The indicator is the number of drug users trying to use. The program aims to increase people's healthy lifestyles without drug abuse. Activities to pregnant women, vulnerable communities, students, students, and workers who behave in a healthy life and do not abuse drugs. Increasing policies that support the establishment of a culture of healthy living without drug abuse in educational institutions, private work institutions, government institutions, and social organizations.
- b) Pillars of Community Empowerment. The implementation target is to increase public awareness and concern in handling P4GNPN. Indicators of community participation in P4GNPN efforts. The program's objectives are increased awareness, participation, and community independence in P4GNPN steps. For example, the number who report themselves to IPWL, The number of community-owned rehabilitation and post-rehabilitation institutions formed, public information about the illicit circulation of drugs, active activists (volunteers) who carry out drug abuse prevention, and vulnerable communities that clean up drugs through alternative empowerment. Activity Targets are the increase in educational institutions, private work institutions, and government institutions that actively participate in P4GNPN independently, the growth in vulnerable areas and vulnerable community groups that are clean of drugs through alternative empowerment.
- c) Rehabilitation Pillar, The implementation goal is to increase the recovery efforts of drug addicts through comprehensive and continuous rehabilitation services. The indicator is the number of drug addicts who completed the rehabilitation program (Legally Problematic/Voluntary) The number of drug addicts who have received rehabilitation does not recur. The program's objectives are the increase in drug addicts rehabilitated at

government agencies and community components and former drug addicts undergoing post-rehabilitation.

- d) Eradication Pillar, Implementation Objectives are increasing network disclosures, confiscation of evidence, and assets of illicit drug trafficking syndicates. Indicator: The number of drug crime syndicate networks exposed. The value of the support of the seized drug crime syndicate network. The program's objectives include increasing the disclosure of drug crime syndicate networks and seizing drug crime syndicate network assets. Indicator: The number of drug crime syndicate networks exposed.

1. Challenges in P4GN Policy

Considering the broad scope of drug abuse that must be faced by BNN and other relevant government and non-government agencies, some of the challenges that must be understood in the implementation of drug abuse mitigation policies in Indonesia are regarding (i) policy implementation priorities and (ii) gaps in the implementation of decriminalization policies that include mindsets, systems that do not work optimally, gaps between infrastructure and service targets rehabilitation, as well as more proven methods of rehabilitation. Currently, Indonesia is faced with the target of 'Drug-Free 2025' in the context of 'Drug-Free ASEAN 2025.' The phrase 'Indonesia Drug Emergency' or 'Drug Disaster' has shown that with the help of the Organizational Maturity Model in Drug Management. The level of maturity of the drug-related social environment is at the basic level of oversight. That is, the number of abusers is so large, and what is needed is eradication with countermeasures that align with its class. Analogous to the phenomenon of corruption, if the number of corrupt practices is so large (in various lines of government and community bureaucracies, for example), then the countermeasures method taken is eradicating corruption up to a specific social maturity to be applied to the following process. For example, policy and public discussion issues.

In the context of BNN's activities, it can be questioned which policies are the main focus of tackling drug abuse. This means that it is prioritized as a significant and fundamental policy with the logic that its activities can withstand the rate of drug abuse. This is also early detection of drug abuse, so other policies are necessary to create an environment free of drugs. The priority of implementing this policy is also indicative of efficiency and effectiveness. Policy evaluation will re-discuss policy implementation. This stage focuses on identifying the results and consequences of policy implementation. Policy evaluation will provide feedback on whether an existing policy needs to be continued or terminated. There is also the view that policy evaluation is not just about determining whether it succeeds but can also concern a broader perspective. Parsons, (1995) states that policy evaluation is learning about the consequences of the policy.

In general, Rossi et al., (2004) state four reasons why policy evaluations are carried out, namely to:

- a) Assess the ongoing program's feasibility and estimate the improvement efforts' practicality.
- b) Assess the practicality of innovative program initiatives.

- c) Improve the effectiveness of program administration and management.
- d) Meet various accountability requirements.

Evaluation of policies as activities that include substance, implementation and impact. Evaluation is seen as functional activity. This means that policy evaluation is not only carried out at the final stage but can be carried out in the entire policy process. Why should we know and understand every policy that exists? Because policies cannot be understood textually, but so many things are implied (contextual), they are not known to the public in setting policies. The role of the media as a facilitator for the transformation of information to the people is necessary to help this situation. Each existing media is independent or unaffected by any particular political power.

In practice, it is difficult to explain which policies are the priority because all policies are implemented proleptically in the same period of activity time. Each has a different policy direction but with the same size of crunch. The vagueness of the priorities for the implementation of this policy is an accumulation of internal problems of institutional authorities, namely, (1) limited personnel, equipment and technology, (2) limited operational budgets, (3) low welfare of human resources (HR), (4) high sectoral egos. As a result, the prioritization of policy implementation takes into account the availability of personnel, equipment and technology, as well as the availability of operational budgets for activities, rather than the policy's objectives. Regarding the issue of sectoral egos, there are still differences in perceptions about the working mechanism and policy direction between stakeholders, namely BNN and its substructures. Another challenge is the duality of authority and function (overlapping authority/taking over functions) between the BNN and other stakeholders, especially the police. Although it is not acknowledged, the police often exercise BNN authority in drug eradication operations, as if they are competing to show which agencies have a better performance. The dilemma is that the police are also given the authority or authority to maintain order and security of the community, so it is challenging to neglect the primary duties and functions in the same field.

D. CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, the author tries to conclude that in an effort to curb the abuse and illicit circulation of drugs, an evolution of policies is needed to provide a burden that can be felt directly by the community. The suggestion is that every change of leadership does not have to change the direction of policy in a revolutionary manner but can continue policies that are still relevant to be implemented.

Funding Details

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Disclosure Statement

The authors declare that they have no competing interests

Data Availability Statement

The datasets used and/or analyzed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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